

Finite Element Modelling of Low Velocity Impact Damage in Composite Laminates

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ABSTRACT

The present work deals with finite element (FE) modelling of damage in composite laminates due to low velocity impact. Geometrically non-linear FE analyses using LS-DYNA3D are presented and compared with impact test results. The FE models employed are 3D brick and 2D shell models with linear elastic, with and without damage, material behaviour. It is concluded that a reliable numerical model, capable of predicting damage, must take into account the coupling between the dynamic response and the evolution of damage, i. e. the damage cannot be predicted from the dynamic response obtained with an analysis ignoring the laminate stiffness degradation due to damage.

Keywords: Graphite-Epoxy Composites, Impact Damage, Finite Element Method

INTRODUCTION

Damage tolerance is an area of primary concern in composite material aircraft structures design. Strength reduction due to impact damage constitutes the limiting design criterion for structures loaded in compression. A low energy impact damage can reduce the static compressive strength to less than 50% of the virgin laminate strength. A substantial loss of strength occurs even for impact levels below the visibility level and consequently, a prime concern associated with impact damage is the potential risk of undetected damage in a structure.

A lot of work, both experimental and analytical, has been devoted to the assessment of damage and the associated strength reduction caused by impact of foreign objects. The effects of local contact damage have been given a lot of attention. As a result, contact indentation laws accounting for local elastic and permanent indentation have been developed [1]. Less attention has been given to effects of other damage types on the dynamic response. Most analytical/numerical work publicly available, e. g. [2], have addressed prediction of damage extent under the assumption that the influence of damage on dynamic response, apart from local contact damage, is small, thereby justifying a non-degraded (uncoupled) analysis in order to capture stress and strain fields during the event. Failure criteria have subsequently been applied to predict the damage size. This work is intended as a first attempt to partially fill this gap by FE-analyses addressing the effects of other predicted damage modes, delamination, matrix and fibre fracture, on the dynamic response.

This research is part of the on-going EEC Brite-Euram programme BE-3159 "Design Methodology for the Improvement of Damage Tolerance within Composite Structures". This project involves a consortium of industry and research institutes formed by BAe, MBB, Fokker, Dornier, NLR, KU Leuven, Imperial College and Saab Military Aircraft. This paper presents an overview of the modelling work carried out at Saab Military Aircraft.

EXPERIMENTS

The experimental results cited in this paper are part of an investigation carried out by Imperial College within the framework of BE-3159 [3]. Eight-ply quasi-isotropic test specimens with $[+45/-45/90/0]_8$ layup and a thickness of 1 mm have been fabricated using Ciba-Geigy 6376C-HTA unidirectional carbon fibre prepreg. Each specimen, 150 by 100 mm in size, was impacted once in the centre of the plate using a 0.42 kg instrumented impactor with a hemispherical 12.7 mm diameter tip. Specimens were subjected to impact energies in the 0.31 J to 3.11 J range with clamped boundary conditions in a support rig with a 125x75 mm aperture.

The impact parameters, selected to be representative of impact by e.g. dropped tools, justify a quasi-static analysis; the maximum deflection of the plate and maximum impact force coincide in time since the plate inertial forces are negligible.

FE-MODELS

The geometrically non-linear explicit FE code LS-DYNA3D [4] was utilised to analyse the impact event. When degradation due to damage was included, a linear elastic material behaviour was assumed up to the point of failure. Static stiffness and strength data were used since strain rates in the order of 10 per second have been shown to be of no significance. In all models clamped boundary conditions, restraining both rotations and displacements, were imposed.

The impactor was treated as a rigid body throughout this study. This is deemed satisfactory since the stiffness of the steel impactor is approximately 20 times higher than the transverse stiffness of the composite plate. Local crushing of the laminate at the point of impact was not accounted for in the analyses. This assumption will be discussed further in the results section.

For comparative purposes, a static ABAQUS [5] shell model has been included to relate a simple energy balance approach to dynamic analyses. Assuming conservation of total energy, the elastic plate deformation energy is equated to the kinetic energy of the impactor. The calculated load-deflection curves from static analyses were integrated numerically to obtain the load-energy relation.

LS-DYNA3D 1/4 plate brick element model

A quarter of the plate and impactor was modelled using a total of 1499 8-node brick elements with 1-point integration. The relatively large number of elements (224) forming the impactor are required to accurately model the geometrical shape. The mesh with three bricks through the plate thickness is shown in Figure 1.

A 'smeared' material description was used for the laminated plate. The eight plies of the laminate were grouped in three orthotropic bundles. The correct in-plane stiffness is maintained in this process while the bending stiffness of each bundle is approximated. The validity of the "smeared" material model has been checked using geometrically non-linear ABAQUS layered shell analyses of a centrally loaded plate. The difference in deflection for a load of 700 N was less than 2% for a 'smeared' three layer plate compared to an eight layer plate, which is considered acceptable. It is also concluded that the difference is diminishing as the membrane stresses increase.

The spurious zero-energy modes in the deformable part of the mesh were suppressed by use of hourglass control. In a zone containing the contact area (10x10x3 elements) the Flanagan-Belytschko stiffness form was used to avoid excitation of hourglass modes due to large contact forces. For the remaining elements standard LS-DYNA3D viscous hourglass control was used in order to avoid undue stiffening of the response, which would be the result of using the stiffness form of hourglass control in the entire mesh. A numerical study showed that this combination eliminated the hourglass modes induced by contact forces without affecting the dynamic response. With an average time step of 27 ns approximately one hour of CPU-time on a CRAY XMP-416 was required for an analysis up to a total time of 2.5 ms. When the dynamic response has been obtained, a portion of the coarse model is subsequently refined to obtain a ply-by-ply resolution of stresses and strains (using one brick through-the-thickness of each ply). In the second run, time-history data saved from the first analysis are imposed on the boundaries of the refined model.

LS-DYNA3D 1/4 plate brick element model with delamination failure

The 3D model, as described above, was modified to include interface elements allowing for the formation of two delaminations during impact. The following quadratic delamination criterion implemented in DYNA3D was used:

$$e^2 = \left(\frac{\sigma_z}{X}\right)^2 + \left(\frac{\tau}{Y}\right)^2 \quad (1)$$

where σ_z and τ represent interlaminar peel and shear stress, respectively, X is the interlaminar peel failure stress and Y is the interlaminar shear failure stress. Failure is assumed to occur when $e \geq 1$, and nodes are released accordingly. In failed areas only compressive stresses can be transferred to prevent penetration of material. Friction in the delaminated interface was not considered in the analysis.

LS-DYNA3D 1/4 plate layered shell model

A quarter of the plate was modelled using layered shell elements according to Figure 2. The impactor mesh was the same used in the brick model, while the plate was modelled using 96 4-node layered shell elements. Hourglassing was suppressed by using standard LS-DYNA3D viscous hourglass control. With a time step of 48 ns this model required approximately 12 minutes of CPU-time on a CRAY XMP-416 for an analysis up to a total time of 4.5 ms. Stresses and strains calculated using this model are not expected to be entirely reliable since the layup contain +45 and -45 plies for which symmetry boundary conditions are not applicable.

LS-DYNA3D Full plate layered shell model

The mesh used in the 1/4 plate shell model was mirrored with respect to the symmetry planes to obtain a full plate model without symmetry conditions, Figure 3. Compared with the previous model this increases the CPU-time required by a factor of four. Analyses were carried out with, and without, in-plane damage material behaviour using the Chang-Chang Composite Damage Model [6,7], as implemented in DYNA3D. In-plane failure is predicted and corresponding properties are degraded due to damage by setting appropriate material parameters to zero. Three criteria, equation 2, for matrix, compression and fibre failure are used. A fibre-matrix shearing term, τ^* , augments each damage mode. Failure is assumed to occur whenever $F_{matrix} \geq 1$, $F_{compression} \geq 1$ or $F_{fibre} \geq 1$.

$$\begin{aligned} F_{matrix} &= \left(\frac{\sigma_2}{S_2}\right)^2 + \tau^*, & F_{compression} &= \left(\frac{\sigma_2}{2S_{12}}\right)^2 + \left[\left(\frac{C_2}{2S_{12}}\right)^2 - 1\right] \frac{\sigma_2}{C_2} + \tau^* \\ F_{fibre} &= \left(\frac{\sigma_1}{S_1}\right)^2 + \tau^*, & \tau^* &= \left(\frac{\tau_{12}^2}{2G_{12}} + \frac{3}{4}\alpha\tau_{12}^4\right) / \left(\frac{S_{12}^2}{2G_{12}} + \frac{3}{4}\alpha S_{12}^4\right) \end{aligned} \quad (2)$$

where S_1 , S_2 , C_2 and S_{12} is longitudinal tensile, transverse tensile, transverse compressive and in-plane shear strength, respectively. σ_1 , σ_2 and τ_{12} is ply longitudinal, transverse and shear stress, G_{12} is the shear modulus and α is a non-linear shear stress parameter set to zero in this study. Standard LS-DYNA3D hourglass control was used. In analyses with degradation involving appreciable amounts of fibre damage it was observed that energy was stored by the hourglass control. Switching the hourglass control in the centre region of the plate to the stiffness form reduced the amount of energy stored, though the problem is presently not entirely resolved.

ABAQUS Full plate shell model

A static ABAQUS layered shell model was constructed in order to appraise the validity of a simple energy balance approach. The mesh containing 68 ABAQUS S8R elements is shown in Figure 4. A concentrated load was applied to the centre node of the plate. Both geometrically linear and non-linear analyses without failure were carried out.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The dynamic responses from analyses without damage, for a 0.61 J impact with no detectable damage in the test specimen, using three dynamic models are compared with test data in Figure 5. It is shown that the 1/4 plate brick model and the full plate shell model are in excellent agreement, while the 1/4 plate shell model deviates somewhat. This indicates that great care must be exercised when using symmetry boundary conditions for laminates where symmetry is applicable to the geometry but not to the layup.

Damage prediction and associated effects on the dynamic response

Delamination

In Figure 6 two 3.1 J impact analyses, with and without delamination failure, are compared. When first failure is obtained in the analysis with damage degradation, Figure 7, the associated (first) load drop corresponds to the predicted delamination threshold value. A comparison of the deformed geometry for a central portion of delaminated and non-delaminated plates, Figure 8, show a locally large difference (0.12 mm at the corner node). Yet, the local increase in deflection is small compared with the total displacement (approx. 3%) and the response is therefore little affected by limited delamination. It is concluded that delamination alone dissipates small amounts of energy and accordingly the influence on the dynamic response is small. The limited influence of delaminations on the dynamic response, points to the presence of other damage modes. The predicted damage area, using analyses with only delamination failure included, cannot be expected to correlate well with tests for the complete range of impact energies, as the predicted force history is in poor agreement with test data. (cf. Figure 9).

Contact Indentation

The deformations associated with permanent contact indentation are in the order of a few hundreds of a mm, which is less than the predicted deformations due to delamination alone. It is therefore concluded that energy dissipation due to contact indentation is negligible for the tested plate.

In-plane Matrix and Fibre Failure

Results from full plate shell analyses of a 3.1 J impact, with and without degradation due to damage, are shown in Figure 9 together with the force vs. time curve recorded during tests. During the early stages where only matrix fracture occurred, Figure 10, the force curve is not affected. The limited influence of matrix failure is expected since the matrix contribution to the laminate stiffness is small. The first visible load drop is associated with fibre fracture. An appreciable amount of energy is dissipated due to fibre fracture, resulting in a truncation of the force vs. time curve and a prolonged duration of the event. In Figure 11 force vs. impactor displacement is plotted for analyses with and without damage. The difference corresponds to energy absorbed by the plate during impact.

FE analyses compared with test results

The effects of damage on the dynamic response is shown in Figure 12, where FE-predictions are compared with test results. The large difference between the indicated linear and non-linear response (using geometrically linear and non-linear ABAQUS-analyses and the energy-balance approach) is attributable to membrane stiffening effects due to deflections exceeding the plate thickness. Despite the crude contact load introduction, the energy-balance model works surprisingly well and provides a reasonable estimate of the maximum force during impact when compared with dynamic analyses without damage. The applicability of this model is, however, limited to impact events where conditions are "quasi-static" and the material at hand is not strain rate dependent.

The delamination threshold force for the tested laminate is approximately 700 N, or, in terms of impact energy, 0.6 J. Below this force level no damage is detected using non-destructive inspection (NDI) techniques. This does not exclude the presence of matrix cracks, as predicted in the analysis with damage degradation of the 0.6 J impact, since this form of damage cannot be detected using current NDI techniques. For impact energies only slightly above the damage threshold the geometrically non-linear analyses without degradation starts to deviate from the tests. As the impact energy is further increased, the deviations are more pronounced, resulting in a grossly overpredicted

maximum contact force for the highest impact energy. The curve obtained using an FE-model with degradation due to damage is in better agreement with tests, although the maximum force is still overpredicted in the analyses. This difference in comparison to the non-degraded curve is mainly attributable to fibre fracture. It is therefore suggested that fibre fracture controls the maximum force the plate can sustain and causes the maximum force to "level-off" to a more or less constant value as the impact energy is increased.

Damage area, as determined by C-scan inspection of impacted plates, is plotted vs. impact energy and maximum force in Figure 13. On the front (impact) side of the specimen the only evidence of the impact event is a very shallow dent, which is hardly discernible to the naked eye even for the highest impact energy. Transverse matrix cracks on the back side of the plate are first visible for an incident energy of 1.4 J. As the impact energy is increased above this level these cracks are more pronounced, and the damage area continues to grow although the maximum force does not increase much. It is concluded that further delamination growth is facilitated by the presence of other damage modes (i. e. fibre fracture) present at this stage rather than driven by increased force. A similar conclusion has been arrived at in an experimental work [8].

CONCLUSIONS

It is concluded that the coupling between the dynamic response and stiffness degradation due to damage must be accounted for in a numerical model capable of predicting damage due to impact. Damage during impact is shown to have a large influence on the dynamic response. Damage softens the plate resulting in a truncated force vs. time curve and a prolonged impact event.

Fibre fracture dissipates an appreciable amount of energy, and as a consequence, largely influences the dynamic response. On the other hand, matrix cracks and delaminations seem to dissipate relatively small amounts of energy and have less influence on the dynamic response. For the tested thin plate it is concluded that the energy dissipation due to permanent contact indentation is negligible. Based on FE analyses of the tested plate it is concluded that the main cause of deviation from elastic analyses is fibre fracture. This in turn implies that fibre fracture occurred for impact energies not far above the damage threshold. It is also suggested that fibre fracture causes the maximum force to "level-off" to a constant value as the impact energy is increased.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

This work was partially supported by the Swedish Board for Technical Development (NUTEK). The valuable discussions with colleagues involved in the BE-3159 programme are gratefully appreciated.

REFERENCES

1. Tan, T. M., Sun, C.T., *Use of Static Indentation Laws in the Impact Analysis of Laminated Composite Plates*, J. of Applied Mechanics, Vol. 52, pp. 6-12, March 1985.
2. Choi, H.Y., Chang F.K., *A model for Predicting Damage in Graphite/Epoxy Laminated Composites Resulting from Low-velocity Point Impact*, J. of Composite Materials, Vol. 26, No 14, pp. 2134-2169, 1992.
3. Davies, G.A.O. and Robinson, P., *Predicting Failure by Debonding/Delamination*, Presented at AGARD: 74th Structures & Materials Meeting, Debonding/Delamination of Composites, 1992.
4. LS-DYNA3D, version 911, Livermore Software Technology Corporation.
5. ABAQUS, version 4.9, Hibbitt, Karlsson and Sorensen, Inc.
6. Chang, F.K. and Chang, K.Y., *Post-Failure Analysis of Bolted Composite Joints in Tension or Shear-Out Mode Failure*, J. of Composite Materials, Vol. 21, No 9, pp. 809-833, September 1987.

7. Chang, F.K. and Chang, K.Y., *A Progressive Damage Model for Laminated Composites Containing Stress Concentration*, J. of Composite Materials, Vol. 21, No 9, pp. 834-855, September 1987.
8. Lee, S.M. and Zahuta, P., *Instrumented Impact and Static Indentation of Composites*, J. of Composite Materials, Vol. 25, No X, pp. 204-222, February 1991.

Figure 1. DYNA3D 1/4 plate brick model.

Figure 2. DYNA3D 1/4 plate shell model.

Figure 3. DYNA3D full plate shell model.

Figure 4. ABAQUS full plate shell model.

Figure 5. Dynamic response calculated using three different DYNA3D models compared to test data. 0.61 J impact.

Figure 6. Force vs. time. With/without delamination failure. 3.1 J impact.

Figure 7. Predicted delamination area. 3.1 J impact.

Figure 8. Deformed geometry with/without delamination. 3.1 J impact.

Figure 9. Force vs. time prediction compared to tests. 3.1 J impact.

Figure 10. Damage predicted in FE-analysis.

Figure 11. Force vs. impactor displacement. 3.1 J impact.

Figure 12. Maximum force vs. Impact energy. Analyses and tests.

Figure 13. Damage area vs. maximum impact force and impact energy.